

Meeting Minutes

EMA-SAWP DM: Qualification Advice on *in silico* simulator of the progression of pulmonary tuberculosis to inform vaccine dose decision-making in phase IIa clinical trials

Venue: On-line Meeting

Date: 25th September 2023, at 14:00 - 16:00

Participants:

- **QA-Applicants:**
 - o Giulia Russo (MIMESIS SRL) - GR
 - o Francesco Pappalardo (UNICT) - FP
 - o Valentina di Salvatore (UNICT) - VdS
 - o Matteo Balestri (MIMESIS SRL) - MB
- **EMA-SAWP:**
 - o Flora Musuamba Tshinanu - FMT
 - o Efthymios Manolis - EM
 - o Olivia Capanna - OC
 - o Dieter Deforce - DD
 - o Fabrizio Chiodo - FC
 - o Jens Reinhardt - JR
 - o Linda Marchioro - LM

Presentation File: pres UISS-TB-DR EMA meeting Sept2023 final_ListOfParticipant.pptx

Minutes were uploaded in IRIS by the QA-Applicants on 29th September 2023

14.10 – Round of presentation from both SAWP members and the applicants; start of procedure.

Q&A session:

Slides 7 to 12 (Question 1): FMT asks about figure in slide 8 and gives her interpretation of the figure "*Escalation dose predictions by UISS-TB-DR*". FP explains that in the patient validation study the optimal dosage is 25 mg, which is confirmed by the simulations. But 30mg would be a good dosage as well, even if this result needs to be validated by a clinical study. FMT communicates her doubts about the possible results between 25mg and 30mg doses which are missing. Then FMT says the three-dosages model would be better for immunotherapy rather than vaccines. EM asks about the reason behind the choice of RUTI vaccine and FP talks about STriTuVaD experience. FMT asks how FP would validate his model if he was free to choose the clinical data to collect considering that the current available data cannot validate the proposed dose. FP answers that a clinical trial with the 3 doses would be necessary, but this is out of QA-Applicant scope.

LM asks whether the validation data come from the same source where input data come from. FP replies that the input parameters used for UISS-TB model are the same coming from the cohort of the performed clinical trial. She also asks what data are used to tune the treatment layer. FP replies that those data do not come the same clinical trial, but from pre-

clinical and early clinical studies of the RUTI vaccine. FP explains the reason why other vaccines similar to RUTI could be also simulated with UISS-TB.

DD asks for confirmation that no data from clinical study are used to both construct and validate the model. FP confirms.

EM asks about the correlations between all parameters. FP explains that individual analyses for each parameter were performed to verify the effect of other parameters. Those analyses are independent from the validation dataset of the clinical study.

FMT asks about demographic parameters such as body size, BMI. FP explains that hundred of digital twins were simulated to achieve two targets. The first one is to represent a broader population; the second one is to guarantee that stochastic variability within HLA and environmental variations do not affect the simulations results.

FC makes a comment about the usage of mathematics in translating biology into a computational model, which he particularly appreciated. Then he asks why limiting to IFN-gamma and not test also the other parameters (ILs, TNF-alfa...). FP replies that many outputs parameters were simulated, but only for IFN-gamma validation data were available.

Slide 13, about CoU. No questions.

Slide 15 (Question 2): FMT asks for a short confirmation “(no the long Italian say)” if the interpretation she gives of the ranges of the sputum conversion plots are correct – FP confirms. Furthermore, she asks if it would be easier finding clinical data for the evaluation of sputum culture in patients treated with antibiotics rather than finding clinical data for the validation of the model in its current status. FMT and DD say that they are more interested in the sputum culture data than INF-gamma data also in terms of market application decision. FP highlights that the QA is related to immunogenicity not to efficacy so IFN-gamma is a well-accepted biomarkers in this context.

Slide 17 (Question 3): All questions were already answered in previous discussion – no further discussion necessary.

Slide 19 (Question 4): FC asks in which scenario FP would give the patient the highest dose and in which scenario he would give the lowest dose. FP clarifies the different scenarios.

Slide 21 (Question 5): FMT says that they see a potential in the model we propose. There are 2 layers of difficulty:

1. They need to be sure that the model is robust and works as stated, but due to the technical difficulty in the verification they need to trust the proposer.

2. The clinical validation data are limited: the fact that the model works only for RUTI prevents the possibility to have the QA.

FP makes two comments:

1. about inspection: data are publicly available; the proposed pipeline is totally independent from any data manipulation. Furthermore, model’s credibility has been formally assessed using ASME VV40 and unity tests; finally, UISS simulation core owns tenth of published articles in renowned peer review journals.

2. about RUTI vaccine: RUTI is just a working example for the proposed methodology, not a limitation. EM says that more examples are needed for them to be convinced of the efficacy of the model for that CoU. The wider the application the more convincing the model will be.

FMT stress again that EMA-SAWP see potential, and they are willing to support the QA-Applicants, but RUTI example is not enough to convince EMA-SAWP that the model is robust and works for other treatments and she express her wonder about how the UISS-TB is working that well for RUTI (“magical the way predicting the data”) and EMA-SAWP cannot trust that it will work for wider applications.

Slide 24 (Question 6) – no questions.

EM asks how the platform can simulate INF-gamma levels. FMT says that they still have doubts in considering INF-gamma as the perfect biomarker for TB. FP answers that INF-gamma is a well-known TB marker widely discussed in literature data, as reported on the last version of the Briefing Book.

EM asks what the next steps are. FP answers explaining that data of Indian TB patients from STriTuVaD project are about to be disclosed, and this will allow the prospective validation of model’s results.

Wrap-up conclusion:

The EMA-SAWP sees a potential in UISS-TB-DR as a simulation tool, but EMA-SAWP have some doubts the way the QA-Applicants are making the Qualification Advice request, because:

- EMA-SAWP cannot yet confirm that UISS-TB-DR is robust and works as stated. An on-site investigation of the tool would be useful, but not part of this QA.
- The model is based on RUTI data only and validates RUTI vaccine only. This is a too small CoU which does not need a qualification advice. The data available to validate the tool are not enough to validate similar vaccine treatments: EMA needs validation on (prospectively collected) independent clinical data in diverse scenarios to give the QA.
- Independent data are necessary to show that the UISS-TB works in those independent scenarios.
- EMA-SAWP still have some doubts about using INF-gamma as biomarker.

Furthermore, EMA-SAWP suggest that QA-Applicants should convince pharmaceutical companies to use UISS-TB so that prospective data to validate the model will be generated.

QA-Applicants expressed doubts about how to perform the credibility assessment in a bigger scenario than RUTI only and how to convince regulatory agencies.

16:00 – End of meeting.